

Managing Green-Oriented Demand and Reliability in Inventory Systems Using Dual-Level Trade Credit Policies

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Abstract: This study explores optimal production and inventory strategies for environmentally friendly products within a dual trade credit framework. With consumer demand increasingly shifting toward sustainable products and rising market competitiveness, companies face the dual challenge of maintaining product quality while offering competitive pricing. This research models a deteriorating inventory system in which production exceeds immediate demand to avoid shortages. Trade credit is introduced as a strategic mechanism to stimulate customer demand, and its influence on overall system performance is analyzed. The model integrates reliability as a key production consideration, enhancing operational efficiency and product quality. The main objective is to minimize total costs by determining optimal production and inventory policies under various trade credit scenarios. Numerical simulations and optimization are conducted using Maple 18 software, supported by a sensitivity analysis to evaluate the effects of critical parameters. The findings offer insights into the interaction between green production, trade credit schemes, reliability, and quadratic demand within sustainable supply chain management.

Keywords: Green technology, dual trade credit, reliability, inventory optimization, deterioration, partial trade credit, quadratic demand.

1. Introduction

Traditional inventory models typically assume constant demand, but growing environmental awareness has prompted businesses to adopt green technologies and sustainable products to reduce pollution. This shift brings new challenges in offering high-quality eco-friendly products at competitive prices within constrained timelines. Trade credit is commonly employed in retail to enhance sales—allowing retailers to delay payment without incurring interest, provided payments are made within the specified credit period. This mechanism helps retailers manage cash flow and generate additional interest income. However, late payments often lead to high-interest penalties from manufacturers

2. Literature Review

2.1 Deterioration and Demand Variability

Yang et al. [30] analyzed supply chains dealing with deteriorating items across multiple retailers, incorporating price-sensitive demand. Khan et al. [9] and Singh et al. [20] developed inventory models that integrate product deterioration, reliability considerations, and trade credit schemes. Shah et al. studied economic order quantity (EOQ) under inflation with time- and advertisement-sensitive demand. Tiwari et al. [26] explored pricing models for perishable goods, including expiration dates and two-level partial trade credit scenarios. Tayal et al. [23] proposed an inventory model with stock- and price-sensitive demand, variable holding costs, and partial backlogging under trade credit. Giri et al. [3] examined closed-loop supply chains emphasizing environmentally conscious consumers and revenue-sharing strategies. Sharma et al. discussed expiry-based inventory models with time-dependent holding costs. Wu et al. [25] investigated the effects of carbon reduction initiatives on supply chain coordination, especially in vendor-managed inventory contexts. These studies collectively highlight the importance of managing perishability, demand uncertainty, and trade credit in modern supply chains.

2.2 Green Production and Pricing

Ghosh et al. [2] explored how green procurement costs and regulatory frameworks affect single-firm and duopoly strategies. Giri et al. [3, 4, 5] proposed several models considering green-sensitive and price-sensitive demand, incorporating warranty policies, revenue-sharing, and imperfect production systems. Yuan et al. [32] modeled quantity-flexibility contracts for eco-conscious demand in the automotive sector, assuming retailers set prices while manufacturers determine green levels. Manna et al. [16] employed interval-valued demand to analyze green production under faulty rate scenarios. Grundey et al. [6] focused on green marketing and eco-labeling, arguing that consumers may compromise preferences to support sustainable practices. Datta et al. analyzed production-inventory systems impacted by green investment and carbon taxes.

2.3 Reliability and Trade Credit Policies

Goyal (1985) introduced trade credit in inventory models, where the supplier allows the retailer a deferred payment period. Huang (2003) extended this by creating an EOQ model involving manufacturer and retailer credit terms. Huang and Hsu (2008) advanced the model to include full supplier credit but partial customer credit. Teng et al. [24] introduced EOQ models with non-decreasing demand.

Mahapatra et al. [12] incorporated reliability using a fuzzy inventory model with Weibull deterioration. Shaikh et al. [21, 22] examined variable demand and different trade credit terms across two warehouses and considered preservation technologies. Singh et al. [20] studied green-sensitive demand and price sensitivity under dual partial trade credit systems. Mahata et al. [14] introduced a vendor-retailer-customer chain with credit-period-based demand. Mohanta et al. [17] proposed a neutrosophic EOQ model with trade credit and marketing-sensitive demand. Jabbarzadeh et al. [8] and Moradi et al. [18] explored trade credit under fuzzy conditions and its effects on profitability. Maji et al. [15] focused on optimizing production reliability in complex system configurations.

2.4 Research Gap and Contribution

With the growing emphasis on sustainability, firms are increasingly adopting green technologies to mitigate environmental impacts. This study presents an EPQ (Economic Production Quantity) model for deteriorating items that considers partial trade credit and

green-sensitive demand. A summary comparison in Table 1 illustrates how this work differs from earlier studies.

Key Contributions:

- **Green-Sensitive and Price-Sensitive Demand:** The model integrates both green-conscious and price-sensitive consumer behavior to enhance demand realism.
- **Two-Level Trade Credit:** By introducing dual-layer trade credit (supplier-to-manufacturer and manufacturer-to-retailer), the model better reflects modern financial arrangements and enhances liquidity.
- **Reliability Integration:** Incorporating reliability as a decision variable reduces quality issues, supports efficient production processes, and promotes continuous improvement.

Research Gap and Uniqueness of this research

Research Article	Type of credit period	Reliability	Demand Type	Deterioration
Singh. <i>et.al</i> (2014)	Full trade credit	✓	Time dependent	✓
Shaikh. <i>et.al</i> (2017)	Alternative	✗	Time and price dependent	✓
Mahapatra <i>et.al</i> (2019)	NA	✓	Price and stock dependent Demand	✓
Maji <i>et. al.</i> (2020)	NA	✓	Reliability and selling Price dependent	✗
Kumar <i>et. al.</i> (2020)	Full trade credit	✓	Advertisement ,time and selling price dependent	✓
Duary. <i>et.al.</i> (2021)	NA	✗	Displayed stock level and selling Price	✓
Tayal <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Full trade credit	✗	Price and stock dependent	✓
Singh <i>et al</i> (2022)	NA	✗	Price and Green sensitive	✓
Handa <i>et. al</i> (2022)	Two level trade credit	✗	Constant	✓

Ummeferva. <i>et.al</i> (2022)	Partial trade credit	✓	Selling price and green quality dependent	✓
Huang <i>et.al</i> (2008)	Partial trade credit	✓	Time dependent	✗
Manna <i>et.al</i> (2022)	NA	✗	Selling price and green quantity	✓
Mohanta. <i>et.al</i> (2022)	Two level partial tred credit	✗	Time dependent	✓
This Article	Two level trade credit	✓	Green Quality ,Time, Reliability And price dependent	✓

NA- Not Available

Table1 Recent research works in the inventory literature

3. Notations and Assumptions

3.1. Parameters

P_c	Production rate (Units)
S	Production cost per cycle(in Dollars)
A	Fixed order Quantity (Dollars/Order)
p_s	Selling price(\$/unit)
C_{hc}	Holding cost (Dollar/Unit)
C_{dc}	Deterioration cost(Dollars/Unit)
R	Reliability rate to Produce good items (%)
I_e	Manufactured earned interest (%)
I_p	Manufactured paid interest (%)
HC	Total holding cost for storing the item(\$)
DC	Total deterioration cost (\$)
θ	Deterioration rate co-efficient(constant)
M	Trade credit period of the manufacturer provided by the supplier(years)
N	Trade credit period of the customers provided by the manufacturer(years)
$I_1(t)$	Trade credit period of the customers provided by the manufacturer(years)

$I_2(t)$	Inventory level at any time interval $t_1 < t < T$ (Units)
β	Green quality of the product (constant)
η	Price elasticity factor(constant)
Z	The total purchase price to be paid by the customer to the manufacturer

3.2 Decision variable

p_s	Selling price (in \$)
T	Replenishment cycle length (in years)
t_1	The total purchase price to be paid by the customer to the manufacturer (In years))
Functions	
$I_{t_1}(t)$	Inventory level at time $t, t \in (0, t_1)$
$I_{t_2}(t)$	Inventory level at time $t, t \in (t_1, T)$
$TC(p_s, T, t_1)$	Total Cost Function(\$)
$D(p_s, t)$	Demand rate.

3.3 Optimal values

T^*	Optimal cycle length
P_s^*	Optimal selling price
t_1^*	Optimal time at which Production stopped
TC^*	Total profit per unit per year (in Dollars)

3.4 Assumptions

1. The model accounts for deterioration, assuming a constant deterioration rate.
2. The manufacturer ensures a reliable production process for the items.
3. An infinite planning horizon is considered in the model.
4. The model incorporates a trade credit policy to enhance the business relationship between the retailer and the customer. In this policy, the manufacturer offers trade credit to the retailer, who in turn extends it to the customer.
5. Demand is price ,time and green sensitive dependent.
6. $D(p_s, t) = (a + bt - ct^2) \cdot \frac{\beta}{1+\beta} \cdot p_s^{-\eta}$ where a is a scale demand, $0 \leq a \leq 1$, b is a linear change of demand, $0 \leq b \leq 1$, c is a quadratic change in demand, $0 \leq c < 1$, $\eta > 1$, $0 \leq \eta < 1$, is a stock elasticity

4. Mathematical Model

This business model begins at the producer's production plant, with production starting at time $t=0$. The period between $t=0$ and $t=t_1$ influences the model in three key ways: production, aggregate customer demand, and deterioration. Production ceases at time $t=t_1$. During the interval $[t_1, T]$, overall customer demand and the rate of deterioration impact inventory levels. To analyze the manufacturer's inventory during this period, the model can be represented mathematically using the following first-order linear differential equations

$$\frac{dI_1}{dt} = \left(\frac{-\beta}{1+\beta}\right) (a + bt - ct^2) * p_s^{-\eta} + r.P_c - \theta.I_1, 0 \leq t \leq t_1$$

Inventory level $I_1(t)$, during time-period $[0, t_1]$ is calculated by the above linear differential equation with boundary condition $I_1(0)=0$ and $I_2(T) = 0$

With boundary condition $I_2(t) = t_1$ and $I_2(t) = T$

$$\frac{dI_2(t)}{dt} + \theta_0 I_2(t) = (a + bt - ct^2) \cdot \left(\frac{-\beta}{1+\beta}\right) \cdot p_s^{-\eta}, \quad t_1 \leq t \leq T \quad (8)$$

Solving the above differential equation, we obtained

$$\frac{dI_2(t)}{dt} + \theta_0 I_2(t) = (a + bt - ct^2) \left(\frac{-\beta}{1+\beta}\right), t_1 \leq t \leq T$$

Solving the above differential equation, we obtain

$$I_2 = (((-ct_1^2 + bt_1 + a)\theta^2 + (2ct_1 - b)\theta^2 c)(e^{\theta t_1} + e^{\theta T}((T^2 - Tb - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc + b)\theta + 2c)) + \beta p_s^{-\eta} - \eta + c2\theta^3(1 + \beta))e^{-\theta t} / \theta^3(1 + \beta)$$

Now the total cost of the inventory is calculated using the following components:

4.1 Ordering Cost: Ordering Cost refers to the expenses incurred in procuring the required quantity and type of materials. If A represents the ordering cost per cycle, then the Ordering Cost can be calculated as:

$$\text{Ordering Cost} = A$$

4.2 Holding Cost: Holding cost refers to the expense incurred for storing goods in a warehouse from the moment they are received until they are sold. If the holding cost per unit per time is denoted as c_{hc} , then the total holding cost for storing the items in the warehouse from time 0 to time T will be:

$$\text{Holding Cost HC} = c_{hc} \left[\int_0^{t_1} I(t) e^{\theta t} dt + \int_{t_1}^T I(t) dt \right]$$

4.3 Deterioration Cost: Deterioration is a natural phenomenon that occurs in many perishable items. If the deterioration cost per unit of time is denoted as c_{dc} the total deterioration cost can be expressed as:

$$\text{Deterioration Cost DC} = c_{dc} \theta \left[\int_0^{t_1} I(t) e^{\theta t} dt + \int_{t_1}^T I(t) dt \right]$$

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$$\text{Deterioration Cost DC} = c_{dc}\theta \left[\int_0^{t_1} I(t)e^{\theta t} dt + \int_{t_1}^T I(t) dt \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DC} &= \\ & \frac{1}{\theta(1+\beta)} \left((p_s^{-\eta} ((c_{t_1}^2 - b_{t_1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2c_{t_1} + b)\theta + 2c)\beta e^{-\theta(T-t_1)} + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)(t_1 - T)\theta^3 + \right. \\ & (-T^2 c - Tb - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc + b)\theta + 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \beta e^{-\theta(T-t_1)} + (-\beta(\theta^3 a + \theta^2 a - b\theta - 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \\ & + \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t_1 - PC e^{\theta t_1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) e^{-\theta t_1} + (((c_{t_1}^2 - b_{t_1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc_{t_1} + b)\theta + 2c) e^{\theta t_1} \\ & + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)t_1 + T^3 c - T^2 b - Ta + a)\theta^3 + (-T^2 c - 2c_{t_1}^2 + Tb + 2b_{t_1} + 4a)\theta^2 + \\ & \left. (2Tc + 4c_{t_1} - 4b) - 8c\right) \beta p_s^{-\eta} - \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t_1 - PC e^{\theta t_1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta) c_{dc} \end{aligned}$$

Two distinct scenarios can arise based on the credit period durations being considered:

outcomes are possible.

Case 1: $N < M \leq t_1 < T$

In this case When the time t_1 exceeds the manufacturer's credit period M , the manufacturer earns interest during the time interval $[0, M]$ and pays interest over the period $[M, T]$ In this scenario, the manufacturer's interest earned and payable can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Interest paid} = I_p = \frac{Sp_1}{T} \left[\int_M^{t_1} I(t) dt + \int_{t_1}^T I(t) dt \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \\ & \frac{1}{\theta(1+\beta)T} \left(S((-\beta((c_{t_1}^2 - b_{t_1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2c_{t_1} + b)\theta + 2c)\beta e^{-\theta(T-t_1)} + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)(t_1 - T)\theta^3 + \right. \\ & (-T^2 c - Tb - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc + b)\theta + 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \beta e^{-\theta(T-t_1)} + (-\beta(\theta^3 a + \theta^2 a - b\theta - 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \\ & + \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t_1 - PC e^{\theta t_1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) e^{-\theta t_1} + (((c_{t_1}^2 - b_{t_1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc_{t_1} + b)\theta + 2c) e^{\theta t_1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Interest Earned} = I_E = \left[\left(\frac{-\beta}{1+\beta} \right) (a + bt - ct^2) \int_0^M t dt + P_c I_{e1} \left(\frac{-\beta}{1+\beta} \right) (a + bt - ct^2) \int_N^M t dt \right]$$

$$= \frac{\beta(c(Z-1)M^4 - \frac{4b(Z-1)M^3}{3} - 2a(Z-1)M^2 + N^2(N^2c - \frac{4}{3}Nb - 2a)) p_s^{1-\eta} I_{e1}}{4(1+\beta)T}$$

Therefore manufacturer's average cost is

Calculation given in Appendix -3

$$\text{TC}_1 = \text{Ordering Cost} + \text{Holding cost} + \text{Deteriorating cost} + \text{Interest paid} - \text{Interest earned}$$

In this scenario, the cycle duration (T) surpasses the maximum delay time permitted by the manufacturer (N). Consequently, the manufacturer is not obligated to pay any interest, meaning $IP = 0$. Additionally, under a partial trade credit arrangement, the manufacturer has the potential to earn interest on the payments collected from customers. This interest can be determined as follows:

Interest earned=

$$I_E = \left(\frac{P_C I_{e_1} Z}{T} \left(\frac{-\beta}{1+\beta} \right) (a + bt - ct^2) \int_0^N t dt + P_C I_{e_1} \left(\frac{-\beta}{1+\beta} \right) (a + bt - ct^2) \int_N^T t dt + \frac{1}{T} \int_T^M dt \right)$$

$$= \frac{\left((-p_s^{-\eta} T^4 c + \frac{4 p_s T^3 b}{3} + 2 p_s T^2 a + (-P_C Z + p_s) (c N^2 - \frac{4}{3} b N - 2a) N^2 \right) I_{e_1} - \frac{4 M^3 c}{3} + \frac{4 T^3 c}{3} + 2 M^2 b - 2 T^2 b + 4 a M - 4 T a \right) p^{-\eta} \beta}{4(1+\beta)T}$$

Therefore manufacturer's average cost is

TC3 = Ordering Cost + Holding cost + Deteriorating cost + Interest paid – Interest earned

Calculation given in appendix -3

Case-3: $T \leq M < N$

Where the cycle length (T) is less than both the customer's credit period (N) and the manufacturer's allowed delay period (M), the supplier is not required to pay any interest to the manufacturer. In this scenario, the interest paid is zero.

Interest Earned = $\left(\frac{P_C I_{e_1} Z}{T} \left(\frac{-\beta}{1+\beta} \right) (a + bt - ct^2) + R P_C \left(\int_0^T t dt + Z \int_T^M T dt + z \int_M^N T dt \right) \right)$

$$I_E = \frac{1}{12 + 12\beta} \left(6T \left(\frac{\beta Z I_{e_1} \left(T^2 c - \frac{4}{3} T b - 2a \right) p_s^{-\eta+1}}{3} + \frac{2 \left(M^3 c - \frac{3 M^2 b}{2} - 3 M a - \left(T^2 c - \frac{3}{2} b - 3 a \right) T \right) Z - M^3 c + \frac{3 M^2 b}{2} + 3 M a + N \left(N^2 c - \frac{3}{2} N b - 3 a \right) \beta p_s^{-\eta}}{3} \right) + P_C (1 + \beta) (I_{e_1} p_s - 2M - 2T) Z - 2M + 2N) R \right)$$

Therefore manufacturer's average cost is

6. Adopted method for calculating optimal solution

6.1 Optimality Algorithm guidelines:

In this section, an algorithmic approach is employed to assess the optimal solution for the overall profit function $TC(T, p_s, t_1)$. The following steps are implemented in Maple 18 software to verify the optimal values of the key parameters.

Step 1: First, use the necessary conditions

$$\frac{\partial TC(T, p_s, t_1)}{\partial T} = 0, \frac{\partial TC(T, p_s, t_1)}{\partial p_s} = 0, \frac{\partial TC(T, p_s, t_1)}{\partial t_1} = 0 \tag{21}$$

One can check that $TC(T, p_s, t_1)$ is a function with a concave shape, yielding distinct and singular values that (T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*) maximize $TC(T, p_s, t_1)$

Step 2: With respect to the decision variables, determine all feasible second-order partial derivatives, expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T^2}, \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T \partial p_s}, \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T \partial t_1}, \\ & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s \partial T}, \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s^2}, \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s \partial t_1}, \\ & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial t_1 \partial T}, \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial t_1 \partial p_s}, \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial t_1^2} \end{aligned}$$

Step 3: Generating the Hessian Matrix

H=

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T \partial p_s} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T \partial t_1} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s \partial t_1} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial t_1 \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial t_1 \partial p_s} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial t_1^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

to establish convexity in the total cost function.

If all Eigenvalues are positive, indicating a positive-definite matrix, the total cost function is convex down, affirming a Minimized total Cost

7. Illustrative Case, Sensitivity Analysis, and Managerial Insights

7.1 Numerical Example:

To verify the formulated model, an example is presented showcasing the optimal solution for the comprehensive cost function $TC(T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*)$. Three examples for three cases have been selected to describe each case of specified inventory model, and all of the solutions are shown in the table.

Solution Methodology

7.2 Algorithm

In this model three case has been arises. To find the optimal solution of the problem Mathematica 12 software has been used. The following steps are performed in the Mathematica 12 software
 Step1: Define the total cost function for case first. Step 2: Put the numerical value of all the parameter.

Step 3: Use the command to minimize the total cost function.

Step 4: Compile and execute. Step 5: Check the output.
 Step 6: There will be two possibilities i.e. solution will be feasible or not. If it is feasible go the step 7 or if it's not feasible go the step 8.
 Step 7: Repeat the process (from step 1 to 6) for all remaining six cases. In all seven cases check in which case total cost is minimum. That will be the optimal case of this problem.
 Step 8: If the solution is not feasible then change the input values and repeat the step from 3 to 8. This process should be followed until the feasible solution is not obtained.

Seven examples for seven cases have been selected to describe each case of specified inventory model, and all of the solutions are shown in the table.

EXAMPLES	TIME RANGE	PRICE	PRODUCTION END TIME	CYCLE LENGTH	TOTAL COST
CASE-1	$N < M \leq t_1 < T$	8.122177439	1.143174487	3.22326245	5.308153
CASE-2	$N < t_1 < T \leq M$	6.45148574	1.6219413553	2.846125344	5.3995076
CASE-3	$t_1 < T \leq M < N$	1.014616621	1.048759188	1.053549715	3.81022215

Table -2

From above table we can identify in the case of 3 optimum solution obtained

Example: Consider the following data

$A = \$ 2$, $c_{hc} = 0.07 \$/unit$, $c_{dc} = 0.79 \$/unit$, $P = 100$ units, $r = 0.065$, $S = 4 \$/unit$,
 $\theta = 31\%$, $a = 1000$, $\beta = 0.01$, $b = 10\%$, $c = 15\%$, $M = 1.89$ yr, $N = 0.1$ yr,
 $I_p = 10\%$, $I_e = 10\%$, $Z = 0.06$, $\eta = 1.07$

The Optimal replenishment cycle length $T^* = 1.053549715y$

The Optimal Selling price $p_s^* = \$1.014616621$

The Optimal ending time when production stopped $t_1^* = 1.048758$ yr.

The Optimal total Cost $TC^* = \$3.81022215$

Then computing all the Eigen values of below stated Hessian matrix H at the Optimal point

$$D_1 = \left| \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T^2} \right| = 0.37599 > 0$$

$$D_2 = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T \partial p_s} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s^2} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$D_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 0.375946475 & 0.00961953188 \\ 0.00961953188 & 0.8325163 \end{vmatrix} = 0.03120562145 \geq 0$$

$$D_3 = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T \partial p_s} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial T \partial t_1} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial p_s \partial t_1} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial t_1 \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial t_1 \partial p_s} & \frac{\partial^2 TC((T^*, p_s^*, t_1^*))}{\partial t_1^2} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$D_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.375946475 & \mathbf{0.00961953188} & -\mathbf{0.1367286481e^{-1}} \\ \mathbf{0.00961953188} & \mathbf{0.8325163} & \mathbf{4.537804898} \\ -\mathbf{0.136728648e^{-1}} & -\mathbf{4.537804898} & -\mathbf{2.852658705} \end{bmatrix}$$

$D_3 = 7.652332435 > 0$

7.2 Sensitivity Analysis of various Inventory Parameters

Inventory parameters	P (selling price)	T (cycle length)	t1 (time at which production end)	TC (total cost)
A	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.048759188	3.41022215
	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.048759188	3.61022215
	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.048759188	4.01022215
	1.014616621	1.014616621	1.048759188	4.21022215
C_{hc}	1.018975051	1.053588480	1.055716920	3.53929190
	1.016756152	1.053524726	1.052168552	3.77477364
	1.010561127	1.053872108,	1.042325552	3.88102629
	1.012552747	1.053664790	1.045480690	3.84563911
C_{dc}	1.031406354	1.055239093	1.075869041	3.56141455
	1.022457723	1.053849028	1.061314123	3.68605347
	1.007705084	1.054362510	1.037813274	3.93400365
	1.001592172	1.056440564	1.028181531	4.05746390
S	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.048759188	3.81022215
	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.048759188	3.81022215
	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.048759188	3.81022215
	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.048759188	3.81022215
P	0.8526595914	1.049445657	1.046676611	4.17723473
	1.122572652	1.056296733,	1.050287064	3.62618992
	0.9263096103	1.051308959	1.047592786	3.99387138
	0.8526595914	1.04944565	1.046676611	4.17723473
R	1.253795293	1.059727979	1.050961816	3.44647885
	1.121162683	1.056286607	1.049738238	3.62835084
	0.9270924675	1.051319036	1.047957502	3.99209329
	0.8538741245	1.049464718	1.047288630	4.17396497
θ	1.057535946	1.009905777	1.098930119	3.64161500
	1.011899562	1.054400474,	1.072617346	3.72813460
	1.018117752	1.057703215	1.026926304	3.88827086
	1.089070798,	1.089070798	1.006696164	3.96268965
a	0.8215526473	1.048590661	1.046987006	3.81189131
	0.9183134351	1.051069709	1.047874165	3.81105801
	1.110534256,	1.056034650	1.049642915	3.80938384
	1.206124948	1.058527678	1.050526001	3.80854324
b	1.053598216	1.053598216	1.014630896	3.41024573
	1.014623758	1.014630896	1.048762000	3.41023388
	1.014704021	1.053615822	1.048743397	3.41014956
	1.053559047,	1.014678820	1.048739745	3.41013495
c	1.048760864	1.048760864	1.048760864	3.81022758
	1.014634683	1.053582228	1.048760026	3.81022492
	1.053484702	1.014580498	1.048757511	3.81021665
Z	1.014651508	1.053538395	1.048744680	3.81015768

	1..9998683712	1.101356075	1.022954247	3.77304164
	1.006734973	1.066178475,	1.035999528	3.79180836
	1.030190413	1.042924377	1.042924377	3.84579689
	1.022486827	1.046796631	1.061283794	3.82821939
I_P	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.04875918	3.81022215
	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.048759188	3.81022215
	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.048759188	3.81022215
	1.014616621	1.053549715	1.048759188	3.81022215
I_E	1.013977510	1.04838065	1.047759640	3.80814235
	1.014295560	1.050948088	1.048258985	3.80918131
	1.014940824	1.056187273	1.049260242	3.81126466
	1.014295560	1.050948088	1.048258985	3.80918131
η	1.018763777	1.053638258	1.049297016	3.81018861
	1.016434098	1.053588257	1.048997080	3.81020740
	1.013159653	1.053519132	1.048565875	3.81023399
	1.011965892,	1.053494293	1.048405672	3.81024381
β	0.9191814071	1.05111817	1.047885155	3.81106360
	0.8231067086	1.048688621	1.047008044	3.81190738
	0.109485430,	1.055985473	1.049630767	3.80938236
	0.8231067086	1.048688621	1.047008044	3.81190738

Table-2: Sensitivity Analysis of various Inventory parameters

8. Over all Conclusion and Future scope.

8.1 Unique contributions of the paper

Limitations of the research

8.1 Future Research Directions

References

1. Datta.T.K(2017) Effect of Green Technology Investment on a Production-Inventory System with Carbon Tax .*Advance in operation Research* .2017(1)
2. Duary, A., Banerjee, T., Shaikh, A. A., Niaki,S. T. A., &Bhunia, A. K. (2021). A Weibull distributed deteriorating inventory model with all-unit discount, advance payment and variable demand via different variants ofPSO. *International Journal of Logistics Systems and Management*, 40(2), 145-170.
3. Ghosh, D., Shah, J., & Swami, S. (2020). Product greening and pricing strategies of firms under green sensitive consumer demand and environmental regulations. *Annals of Operations Research*, 290, 491-520.
4. Giri, B. C., Mondal, C., &Maiti, T. (2018).Analysing a closed-loop supply chain with selling price, warranty period and green sensitive consumer demand under revenue sharing contract. *Journal of Cleaner Produc- tion*, 190, 822-837.

5. Giri, B. C., Dash, A., &Sarkar, A. K. (2020). A single-vendor single-buyer supply chain model with price and green sensitive demand under batch shipment policy and planned backorder. *International Journal of Procurement Management*, 13(3), 299-321.
6. Giri, B. C., & Dash, A. (2022). Optimal batch shipment policy for an imperfect production system under price-, advertisement-and green- sensitive demand. *Journal of Management Analytics*, 9(1), 86-119.
7. Goyal, S. K. (1985). Economic order quantity under conditions of permissible delay in payments. *Journal of the operational research society*, 335-338.
8. Grundey, D., &Zaharia, R. M. (2008). Sustainable incentives in marketing and strategic greening: The cases of Lithuania and Romania. *Technological and Economic Development of Economy*, 14(2), 130-143.
9. Handa, N., Singh, S. R., &Punetha, N. (2022). Impact of carbon emission in two-echelon supply chain inventory decision with controllable deterioration and two-level trade- credit period. *OPSEARCH*, 59(4), 1555-1586
10. Huang, Y. F., & Hsu, K. H. (2008). An EOQ model under retailer partial trade credit policy in supply chain. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 112(2), 655-664.
11. Jabbarzadeh, A., Aliabadi, L., &Yazdanparast, R. (2021). Optimal payment time and replenishment decisions for retailer's inventory system under trade credit and carbon emission constraints. *Operational Research*, 21, 589-620.
12. Khan, A. M., Shaikh, A., Khan A. R., Alrasheedi .A. F. (2023) Advertising and pricing strategies of an inventory model with product freshness-related demand and expiration date-related deterioration. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 73, 353-375.
13. Kumar, M., Chauhan, A., Singh, S. J., &Sahni, M. (2020). An Inventory Model on Preservation Technology with Trade Credits under Demand Rate Dependent on Advertisement, Time and Selling Price. *Accounting and Finance*, 8(3), 65-74.
14. Mahapatra, G. S., Adak, S., &Kaladhar, K. (2019). A fuzzy inventory model with three parameter Weibull deterioration with reliant holding cost and demand incorporating reliability. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 36(6), 5731-5744
15. Mahata, G. C. (2012). An EPQ-based inventory model for exponentially deteriorating items under retailer partial trade credit policy in supply chain. *Expert systems with Applications*, 39(3), 3537-3550
16. Mahata, P., Mahata, G. C., & De, S. K. (2020). An economic order quantity model under two-level partial trade credit for time varying deteriorating items. *International Journal of Systems Science: Operations & Logistics*, 7(1), 1-17.
17. Maji, A., Bhunia, A. K., & Mondal, S. K. (2020). Exploring a production-inventory model with optimal reliability of the production in a parallel-series system. *Journal of Industria and Production Engineering*, 37(2-3), 71-86.
18. Manna, A. K., & Bhunia, A. K. (2022). Investigation of green production inventory Problem with selling price and green level sensitive interval-valued demand via different meta-heuristic algorithms. *Soft Computing*, 26(19), 10409-10421
19. Mohanta, K., Jha, A. K., Dey, A., & Pal, A. (2022). An application of neutrosophic logic on an inventory model with two-level partial trade credit policy for time-dependent perishable products. *Soft Computing*, 1-28.
20. Moradi, S., Gholamian, M. R., & Sepehri, A. (2022). An inventory model for imperfect quality items considering learning effects and partial trade credit policy. *OPSEARCH*, 1-50.
21. Sharma, S., Singh, S., & Singh, S. R. (2018). An inventory model for deteriorating items with expiry date and time varying holding cost. *International Journal of Procurement Management*, 11(5), 650-66
22. Shaikh A. A. (2017). A two warehouse inventory model for deteriorating items with

- variable demand under alternative trade credit policy. *International Journal of Logistics Systems and Management*, 27(1), 40-61
23. Shaikh, A. A., Panda, G. C., Sahu, S., & Das, K. (2019). Economic order quantity model for deteriorating item with preservation technology in time dependent demand with partial backlogging and trade credit. *International Journal of Logistics Systems and Management*, 32(1)
24. Shah, N. H., & Vaghela, C. R. (2017). Economic order quantity for deteriorating items under inflation with time and advertisement dependent demand. *Opsearch*, 54(1), 168-180
25. Singh, S. R., Yadav, D., Sarkar, B., & Sarkar, M. (2021). Impact of energy and carbon emission of a supply chain management with two-level trade-credit policy. *Energies*, 14(6), 1569
26. Singh, S. R. & Ummeferva (2022). Optimal Replenishment Policy For A Green Inventory Model With Price And Green Sensitive Demand Under Reliability. *Global Journal of Modeling and Intelligent Computing*, 2(2), 2767-1917.
27. Tayal, S., Singh, S. R., Katariya, C., & Handa, Shaikh, N. (2021). An Inventory Model with Quantity Dependent Trade Credit for Stock and Price Dependent Demand, Variable Holding Cost and Partial Backlogging. *Reliability: Theory & Applications*, (SI 2 (64)), 225-240
28. Teng, J. T., Min, J., & Pan, Q. (2012). Economic order quantity model with trade credit financing for non-decreasing demand. *Omega*, 40(3), 328-335
29. Pal, P., Bhunia, A. K., & Goyal, S. K. (2007). On optimal partially integrated production and marketing policy with variable demand under flexibility and reliability considerations via Genetic Algorithm. *Applied mathematics*
30. Tiwari, S., Cárdenas-Barrón, L. E., Goh, M., & Shaikh, A. A. (2018). Joint pricing and inventory model for deteriorating items with expiration dates and partial backlogging under two-level partial trade credits in supply chain. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 200, 16-36.
31. Tiwari, S., Ahmed, W., & Sarkar, B. (2019). Sustainable ordering policies for non-instantaneous deteriorating items under carbon emission and multi-trade-credit-policies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 240, 118183.
32. Wu, J., Ouyang, L. Y., Cardenas-Barron, L. E., and Goyal, S. K. (2014). Optimal credit period and lot size for deteriorating items with expiration dates under two-level trade credit financing. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 237, 898-908.
33. Wu, J., and Chan, Y. L. (2014). Lot-sizing policies for deteriorating items with expiration dates and Partial trade credit to credit-risk customers. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 155, 292-301
34. Yang, P. C., Chung, S. L., Wee, H. M., Zahara, E., & Peng, C. Y. (2013). Collaboration for a closed-loop deteriorating inventory supply chain with multi-retailer and price-sensitive demand. *International journal of production economics*, 143(2), 557-566.
35. Yadav, S., & Khanna, A. (2021). Sustainable inventory model for perishable products with expiration date and price reliant demand under carbon tax policy. *Process Integration and Optimization for Sustainability*, 5, 475-486.
36. Yuan, Z., Gong, Y., & Chen, M. (2021). Quantity-Flexibility Contract Models for the Supply Chain with Green-Sensitive Demand in the Automotive Manufacturing Industry. In *Advances in Production Management Systems. Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable and Resilient Production Systems: IFIP WG5.7 International Conference, APMS 2021, Nantes, France, September 5-9, 2021, Proceedings, Part III* (pp. 441-449). Springer International Publishing

37. TC7 = Ordering Cost + Holding cost + Deteriorating cost + Interest paid – Interest earned

APPENDIX-1

CASE-1 $N < M \leq t_1 < T$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\theta(1+\beta)} \left((p_s^{-\eta} ((c_{t_1}^2 - b_{t_1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2c_{t_1} + b)\theta + 2c)\beta e^{-\theta(T-t_1)} + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)(t_1 - T)\theta^3 + \right. \\ & (-T^2 c - Tb - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc + b)\theta + 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \beta e^{-\theta(T-t_1)} + (-\beta(\theta^3 a + \theta^2 a - b\theta - 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \\ & + \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t_1 - PC e^{\theta t_1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) e^{-\theta t_1} + (((c_{t_1}^2 - b_{t_1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc_{t_1} + b)\theta + 2c) e^{\theta t_1} \\ & + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)_{t_1} + T^3 c - T^2 b - Ta + a)\theta^3 + (-T^2 c - 2c_{t_1}^2 + Tb + 2b_{t_1} + 4a)\theta^2 + \\ & (2Tc + 4c_{t_1} - 4b) - 8c) \beta p_s^{-\eta} - \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t_1 - PC e^{\theta t_1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta))_{chc} \left. + \frac{1}{\theta(1+\beta)} \left((p_s^{-\eta} ((c_{t_1}^2 - b_{t_1} - a)\theta^2 \right. \right. \\ & + (-2c_{t_1} + b)\theta + 2c)\beta e^{-\theta(T-t_1)} + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)(t_1 - T)\theta^3 + \\ & (-T^2 c - Tb - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc + b)\theta + 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \beta e^{-\theta(T-t_1)} + (-\beta(\theta^3 a + \theta^2 a - b\theta - 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \\ & + \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t_1 - PC e^{\theta t_1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) e^{-\theta t_1} + (((c_{t_1}^2 - b_{t_1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc_{t_1} + b)\theta + 2c) e^{\theta t_1} \\ & + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)_{t_1} + T^3 c - T^2 b - Ta + a)\theta^3 + (-T^2 c - 2c_{t_1}^2 + Tb + 2b_{t_1} + 4a)\theta^2 + \\ & (2Tc + 4c_{t_1} - 4b) - 8c) \beta p_s^{-\eta} - \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t_1 - PC e^{\theta t_1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta))_{cdc} \left. \right) \\ & + \frac{\beta(c(Z-1)M^4 - \frac{4b(Z-1)M^3}{3} - 2a(Z-1)M^2 + N^2(N^2 c - \frac{4}{3}Nb - 2a)) p_s^{1-\eta} I_{e1}}{4(1+\beta)T} \end{aligned}$$

APPENDIX -2

Case: 2 $N < T \leq M$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & A + \frac{1}{\theta(1+\beta)} ((p_s^{-\eta} ((c_{t1}^2 - b_{t1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2c_{t1} + b)\theta + 2c)\beta e^{-\theta(T-t1)} + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)(t1 - T)\theta^3 + \\
 & (-T^2 c - Tb - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc + b)\theta + 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \beta e^{-\theta(T-t1)} + (-\beta(\theta^3 a + \theta^2 a - b\theta - 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \\
 & + \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t1 - PC e^{\theta t1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) e^{-\theta t1} + (((c_{t1}^2 - b_{t1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc_{t1} + b)\theta + 2c) e^{\theta t1} \\
 & + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)t1 + T^3 c - T^2 b - Ta + a)\theta^3 + (-T^2 c - 2c_{t1}^2 + Tb + 2b_{t1} + 4a)\theta^2 + \\
 & (2Tc + 4c_{t1} - 4b) - 8c)\beta p_s^{-\eta} - \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t1 - PC e^{\theta t1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) cdc) + \frac{1}{\theta(1+\beta)} ((p_s^{-\eta} ((c_{t1}^2 - b_{t1} - a)\theta^2 \\
 & + (-2c_{t1} + b)\theta + 2c)\beta e^{-\theta(T-t1)} + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)(t1 - T)\theta^3 + \\
 & (-T^2 c - Tb - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc + b)\theta + 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \beta e^{-\theta(T-t1)} + (-\beta(\theta^3 a + \theta^2 a - b\theta - 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \\
 & + \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t1 - PC e^{\theta t1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) e^{-\theta t1} + (((c_{t1}^2 - b_{t1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc_{t1} + b)\theta + 2c) e^{\theta t1} \\
 & + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)t1 + T^3 c - T^2 b - Ta + a)\theta^3 + (-T^2 c - 2c_{t1}^2 + Tb + 2b_{t1} + 4a)\theta^2 + \\
 & (2Tc + 4c_{t1} - 4b) - 8c)\beta p_s^{-\eta} - \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t1 - PC e^{\theta t1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) chc) + \\
 & \frac{1}{12 + 12\beta} \left(\frac{\beta Z I_e (T^2 c - \frac{4}{3} Tb - 2a) p_s^{-\eta+1}}{3} \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{2((M^3 c - \frac{3M^2 b}{2} - 3Ma - (T^2 c - \frac{3}{2} b - 3a)T)Z - M^3 c + \frac{3M^2 b}{2} + 3Ma + N(N^2 c - \frac{3}{2} Nb - 3a))\beta p_s^{-\eta}}{3} \right) \\
 & + PC(1 + \beta)(I_e p_s - 2M - 2T)Z - 2M + 2N)R)
 \end{aligned}$$

APPENDIX-3

Case-7: $T \leq M < N$

Therefore manufacturer’s average cost is

TC7 = Ordering Cost + Holding cost + Deteriorating cost + Interest paid – Interest earned

=

$$\begin{aligned}
 & A + \frac{1}{\theta(1+\beta)} ((p_s^{-\eta} ((c_{t1}^2 - b_{t1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2c_{t1} + b)\theta + 2c)\beta e^{-\theta(T-t1)} + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)(t1 - T)\theta^3 + \\
 & (-T^2 c - Tb - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc + b)\theta + 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \beta e^{-\theta(T-t1)} + (-\beta(\theta^3 a + \theta^2 a - b\theta - 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \\
 & + \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t1 - PC e^{\theta t1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) e^{-\theta t1} + (((c_{t1}^2 - b_{t1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc_{t1} + b)\theta + 2c) e^{\theta t1} \\
 & + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)t1 + T^3 c - T^2 b - Ta + a)\theta^3 + (-T^2 c - 2c_{t1}^2 + Tb + 2b_{t1} + 4a)\theta^2 + \\
 & (2Tc + 4c_{t1} - 4b) - 8c)\beta p_s^{-\eta} - \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t1 - PC e^{\theta t1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) cdc) + \frac{1}{\theta(1+\beta)} ((p_s^{-\eta} ((c_{t1}^2 - b_{t1} - a)\theta^2 \\
 & + (-2c_{t1} + b)\theta + 2c)\beta e^{-\theta(T-t1)} + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)(t1 - T)\theta^3 + \\
 & (-T^2 c - Tb - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc + b)\theta + 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \beta e^{-\theta(T-t1)} + (-\beta(\theta^3 a + \theta^2 a - b\theta - 2c) p_s^{-\eta} \\
 & + \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t1 - PC e^{\theta t1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) e^{-\theta t1} + (((c_{t1}^2 - b_{t1} - a)\theta^2 + (-2Tc_{t1} + b)\theta + 2c) e^{\theta t1} \\
 & + ((T^2 c - Tb - a)t1 + T^3 c - T^2 b - Ta + a)\theta^3 + (-T^2 c - 2c_{t1}^2 + Tb + 2b_{t1} + 4a)\theta^2 + \\
 & (2Tc + 4c_{t1} - 4b) - 8c)\beta p_s^{-\eta} - \theta^2 R(\theta p_s t1 - PC e^{\theta t1} + 2 PC)(1 + \beta)) chc) + \\
 & \frac{1}{12 + 12\beta} \left(\frac{\beta Z I_e (T^2 c - \frac{4}{3} Tb - 2a) p_s^{-\eta+1}}{3} \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{2((M^3 c - \frac{3M^2 b}{2} - 3Ma - (T^2 c - \frac{3}{2} b - 3a)T)Z - M^3 c + \frac{3M^2 b}{2} + 3Ma + N(N^2 c - \frac{3}{2} Nb - 3a))\beta p_s^{-\eta}}{3} \right) \\
 & + PC(1 + \beta)(I_e p_s - 2M - 2T)Z - 2M + 2N)R)
 \end{aligned}$$